

Stakeholder perspectives on digital product passports for construction products

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the potential of the digital product passport (DPP) for advancing circularity in the construction sector, in line with the goals of Sustainable Product Initiative and the Construction Products Regulation. Despite its presumed implication for circularity, significant knowledge gaps remain, especially within the construction industry. To address these, the study utilizes semi-structured interviews and a survey to identify the benefits of the DPP, the data needs of key stakeholders, the barriers to implementation as well as the conditions related to efficient implementation. Findings suggest that manufacturing, usage, life-cycle and end-of-life data may form a foundational framework. Key stakeholders identified benefits such as improved traceability and resource efficiency, as well as the potential of integrating with building information modeling, alongside challenges including intellectual property concerns. The study concludes that the DPP should be tailored to each product group, with an optimal level of detail that balances intellectual property while ensuring transparency. Future research should refine the framework by identifying more specific data within each data type.

1. Introduction

The construction sector accounts for substantial impacts in terms of extracted materials, carbon dioxide emissions and generated waste (Heinrich & Lang, 2019). Characterized by a linear economy prominently designed for economic profitability, the industry must adapt to a growing global population, which is expected to reach 9,8 billion by 2050. With two-thirds of people residing in urban areas, the demand for housing will subsequently drive a rise in construction activities (United Nations, 2019). Given the unsustainable nature of the current linear economy, increasing population growth and rapid urbanization, a shift to a circular economy is urgently needed to attain the sustainable development goals (United Nations, 2015).

Barriers for the uptake of secondary raw materials in new construction products have been mapped out in EU projects (e.g. ICEBERG, 2024). These barriers are product-specific and vary along the value chain, and generally include waste quality, complex processing, supply stability uncertainty, economic aspects (low price of virgin raw materials and additional processing costs), and stakeholder knowledge gaps. These barriers are often interlinked. To support recycling practices, specific information must be easily available, up-to-date and contain sufficient information to ensure uptake of construction products with

recycled content (ICEBERG, 2024).

Despite these challenges, the sector is concurrently recognized as having the greatest potential for transitioning to a circular economy (Hossain et al., 2020). Key enablers include traceability and digitalization (Antikainen et al., 2018; European Commission, 2020a), however, current studies on data utilization for circularity often center on single strategies, instead of considering the entire value chain (Acerbi & Taisch, 2020). The European Commission has introduced the digital product passport (DPP) as a policy tool to tackle these issues, addressing the entire value chain with the goal of enhancing circularity. The development of the DPP stems from the Sustainable Product Initiative (SPI) (European Commission, 2022a), supporting the EU Green Deal objectives (European Commission, 2019a). The DPP enables the collection and sharing of product data across the entire value chain, providing traceability when appropriate, thereby promoting circularity and facilitating decision-making through closing information gaps (Koppelaar et al., 2023; Navarro et al., 2022; Ducuing & Reich, 2023). In the development of the new Construction Products Regulation (CPR) (European Commission, 2024a), the DPP is introduced as a mandatory tool by 2028 for construction products regulated through delegated acts of Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) (European Commission, 2024b).

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Although the DPP appears promising, significant literature gaps remain for the construction industry, including a lack of standardization in data content, storage, format, and interoperability. Exploring the data content requirements of each actor in the construction industry is crucial (Jensen et al., 2023), for fully recognizing the potential and benefits, and ensuring its adoption, functionality and effectiveness. Additionally, identifying challenges and barriers to the DPP implementation is necessary to ensure its benefits are effectively realized (Jensen et al., 2023). Further gaps highlight the need for better understanding of multi-actor perspectives, particularly how data requirements vary among different stakeholders (Wicaksono et al., 2025).

The main objective of this article is to explore the benefits of the DPP for key stakeholders in the construction industry with a focus on circularity. It aims to identify the data needs and implementation barriers of the DPP for key stakeholders in the construction industry. This study utilizes a two-fold qualitative approach for the data collection to answer the research questions. This article focuses on construction products, not buildings. It does not cover the DPP system or its technical aspects and underlying IT-infrastructure. To achieve the research objectives, the following research questions are examined:

1. What are the benefits of the DPP for key stakeholders in the construction industry?
2. What are the data content needs for the DPP for construction products?
3. What are the barriers and challenges in implementing the DPP for construction products?
4. How can effective implementation of the DPP for construction products be ensured?

2. Literature review

This section first presents the concept of the DPP. The recognized benefits, data content requirements and the barriers to implementation in the literature are presented thereafter.

2.1. The digital product passport

The DPP is a tool that contains a set of digital data, providing information on the entire life cycle of a product (Koppelaar et al., 2023), including details regarding its origin, composition, repair and end-of-life practices (Götz et al., 2022). Each supply chain actor will access relevant product information for operation or usage (Navarro et al., 2022), while also contributing data to the DPP throughout the product's life cycle (Koppelaar et al., 2023). The primary objective of the DPP is to enhance circularity through addressing information gaps across the value chain by data sharing (Ducuing & Reich, 2023). The tool aims to promote circular economy practices, support circular design, conserve resources, prevent greenwashing and facilitate informed decision-making (Götz et al., 2022; Plociennik et al., 2022b).

The data needs to be stored in either a centralized or decentralized system (Cura et al., 2022). Götz et al. (2022) note that most businesses prefer a decentralized system. Especially blockchain technology as a storage system has gained great attention lately (Canciani et al., 2024; Greiner et al., 2024; Jansen et al., 2022) for its distributed and decentralized database structure, which offers transparency, verifiability and reliability (Meva, 2018; Tezel et al., 2020).

In their review, Plociennik et al. (2022b) define several end-users of a general DPP, categorizing them based on the information source. Herein, material-flow and strategy-oriented actors are identified. The actors associated with the material flow and its processes include: (i) raw material suppliers, (ii) manufacturers, (iii) retailers, (iv) consumers, (v) logistic providers, (vi) repair providers, sorters and recyclers, and (vii) waste management actors. Strategy-oriented actors use data on material flows for decision-making and strategy development, as well as contributing information related to indicators, goals and targets, and

restrictions: (i) research institutions, (ii) government, (iii) certification bodies and (iv) sustainability managers.

2.1.1. The recognized benefits of digital product passports in the literature

The DPP offers benefits encompassing the entire value chain, with numerous potential benefits recognized in the literature, see Table 1. By providing enhanced traceability, the DPP allows stakeholders to make well-informed decisions as well as facilitates various circular practices (e.g. Götz et al., 2022; Walden et al., 2021; Zhang & Seuring, 2024). The DPP facilitates resource optimization and the assessment of future

Table 1
Benefits of the DPP.

Circularity	<p>Facilitates the transition to a circular economy (Abedi et al., 2024; Adisorn et al., 2021; Berger et al., 2023; Canciani et al., 2024; Chaudhuri et al., 2024; Ducuing & Reich, 2023; Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019; Jansen et al., 2023; Navarro et al., 2022; Plociennik et al., 2022b; Walden et al., 2021; Zhang & Seuring, 2024)</p> <p>Enhances traceability and transparency (Adisorn et al., 2021; Berger et al., 2023; Chaudhuri et al., 2024; Götz et al., 2022; Jansen et al., 2023; Plociennik et al., 2022b; Zhang & Seuring, 2024)</p> <p>Fosters sustainable product management (Berger et al., 2023; Canciani et al., 2024)</p> <p>Supports circular design, manufacturing, sourcing, and business models (Berger et al., 2023; Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019; Walden et al., 2021; Watson et al., 2023; Zhang & Seuring, 2024)</p> <p>Retains or increases product and material value (Heinrich & Lang, 2019; Walden et al., 2021), increases recycling rates (Walden et al., 2021), reduces waste and virgin resource consumption (Abedi et al., 2024, Heinrich & Lang, 2019)</p> <p>Supports the concept of buildings functioning as material banks (Götz et al., 2022)</p> <p>Supports industry climate neutrality (Götz et al., 2022)</p> <p>Facilitates low-carbon transition (Adisorn et al., 2021)</p>
Resource efficiency	<p>Supports resource optimization (Heinrich & Lang, 2019) and strategies for energy efficiency (Götz et al., 2022)</p> <p>Facilitates decision-making (Adisorn et al., 2021; Canciani et al., 2024; Chaudhuri et al., 2024; Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019; van Capelleveen et al., 2023; Walden et al., 2021; Watson et al., 2023; Zhang & Seuring, 2024)</p> <p>Enhances collaboration (Plociennik et al., 2022b)</p> <p>Manages supply and demand (Heinrich & Lang, 2019)</p> <p>Improves logistics and reversed logistics (Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019)</p> <p>Cost reductions through resource management (Heinrich & Lang, 2019)</p> <p>Offers competitive advantage (Jansen et al., 2022) and opens new markets (Götz et al., 2022)</p> <p>Improves enforcement tools (Ducuing & Reich, 2023), compliance checks and certification processes (Canciani et al., 2024; Plociennik et al., 2022b)</p> <p>Supports diligence in regulatory requirements (Chaudhuri et al., 2024; Walden et al., 2021)</p> <p>Prevents greenwashing, tracks sustainability claims (Adisorn et al., 2021; Götz et al., 2022)</p> <p>Monitors environmental and socio-economic impacts (Durand et al., 2022)</p>
Data management and utilization	<p>Provides access to reliable, standardized data (Götz et al., 2022; Plociennik et al., 2022b; Walden et al., 2021)</p> <p>Enables data storage, processing and utilization across complex value chains (Götz et al., 2022)</p> <p>Promotes innovative data utilization (Watson et al., 2023)</p> <p>Easier access to information (Ducuing & Reich, 2023; Heinrich & Lang, 2019; Koppelaar et al., 2023)</p> <p>Eliminates informational barriers (Adisorn et al., 2021; Berger et al., 2023; Ducuing & Reich, 2023; Navarro et al., 2022; Walden et al., 2021)</p>

material and product flows, consequently leading to increased product value, reduced waste and higher recycling rates (Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019; Walden et al., 2021). Moreover, it is also acknowledged as a driver of innovation in circular design and business models (Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019; Walden et al., 2021). By providing centralized information in a standardized, comparable format (Walden et al., 2021), the DPP ensures stakeholders have easy access to reliable data while also streamlining data utilization, processing and storage (Götz et al., 2022). Additionally, activities related to due diligence efforts (Walden et al., 2021), certifications and compliance checking (Plociennik et al., 2022b) are streamlined.

Furthermore, integrating the DPP with other digital platforms, such as the building information model (BIM) is a prospect as well. This would enable visualising structures at many levels: materials, products, components, and entire buildings. Combining such information would thus aid interactions between different levels and further increase potential. (Honic et al., 2019).

2.1.2. Data content requirements of the digital product passport

Jensen et al. (2023) outlined 28 data points, which were further categorized into four main data types, including: 1) manufacturing data, 2) usage data, 3) end-of-life data, and 4) life-cycle data (Jansen et al., 2023; Plociennik et al., 2022b). Manufacturing data encompasses details on the manufacturing process, physical and chemical properties, composition, materials and weights in each component, and potential hazardousness (Jensen et al., 2023). Usage data documents changes made to the product, such as replaced or repaired parts, and any damages (Jensen et al., 2023). End-of-life data includes documentation and reporting of collection, sorting and treatment practices, including waste management methods applied (Jensen et al., 2023). Life-cycle data can include guidelines for storage, information on environmental impacts and social life cycle assessments (Jensen et al., 2023).

The previously outlined requirements form a general guideline, differing based on various criteria, e.g. product complexity, life cycle intricacy, product value and harm potential (Plociennik et al., 2022b). Additionally, these requirements are not designed for any specific industry. With complex value chains and varying requirements among actors, a detailed analysis of each actor's needs is necessary to define the DPP contents (Durand et al., 2022).

The Construction Products Regulation (CPR) (European Commission, 2024a) influences the content of the DPP for construction products, including aspects such as assessment, certification, environmental product declarations (EPD) and declarations of performance and conformity (DoPC). Moreover, the DPP could integrate information on chemical substances regulated under REACH (European Commission, 2006) as well as substances of concern under the Waste Framework Directive (European Commission, 2018).

2.1.3. Barriers in the implementation of the digital product passport

Guth-Orlowski (2021) identifies four key requirements regarding the functionality of the DPP: access control, data quality, flexibility and inclusivity. Each requirement is associated with challenges and barriers.

The mechanisms associated with system access control must ensure the protection of intellectual property rights and safeguarding of trade secrets of manufacturers (Guth-Orlowski, 2021). Safeguarding intellectual property as well as ensuring the confidentiality regarding business information are recognized as major challenges (e.g. Berger et al., 2023; Ducuing & Reich, 2023; Kebede et al., 2023). For example, such information includes product composition or supply chain details (Guth-Orlowski, 2021). Product performance data generated and collected during the use-phase, such as consumer data, can support circular practices but may raise privacy concerns (Ducuing & Reich, 2023). Data governance challenges are deemed significant, as its absence presents concerns regarding data management (Ducuing & Reich, 2023).

The data entered into the DPP must be correct, verifiable and reliable (Guth-Orlowski, 2021; Kebede et al., 2023). Essentially, avoiding

“garbage in – garbage out” improves the functionality (Saari et al., 2022). Its contents should adhere to the data minimization principle, including only essential data while keeping the amount to a minimum (Saari et al., 2022). Moreover, end-users may have concerns about data accuracy, future usability and up-to-dateness (Ducuing & Reich, 2023). Given the long lifespan of some construction products, it should be ensured that the data remains accurate for decades.

The DPP should remain flexible and be under continuous development, given the complex nature of global supply and value chains involving numerous actors (Guth-Orlowski, 2021). Adding new organizations or actors to the DPP, as well as removing redundant information and actors should be easy and straightforward (Guth-Orlowski, 2021). This presents a barrier particularly in the construction sector, due to buildings often having various owners and varied occupation profiles (Luscuere, 2017). Moreover, continuous data input during the use-phase can be particularly challenging (Adisorn et al., 2021).

Inclusivity is required to maximize the potential and benefits of the DPP for all actors (Guth-Orlowski, 2021). The DPP must be easy to access and user-friendly (Walden et al., 2021). Factors that potentially present challenges include e.g. technical obstacles (Abedi et al., 2024; Saari et al., 2022), related costs (Abedi et al., 2024; Cura et al., 2022; Saari et al., 2022), geographical barriers (Cura et al., 2022), cultural aspects (Cura et al., 2022), and variations in legal, social, and environmental regulations (Cura et al., 2022). For SMEs, the DPP should avoid contributing with additional burdens related to human resources, associated costs, available infrastructure and data analytics (Cura et al., 2022).

Overall, a key aspect across the four key requirements is the ongoing development of standardization. There is not yet a unified approach to the DPP content, including standardized measurements and metrics like carbon footprint declarations (Walden et al., 2021), collection and storage methods (Cura et al., 2022), and formats for various product types (Abedi et al., 2024; Walden et al., 2021). However, at present, the CEN/CENELEC JTC24 committee has received multiple horizontal standardization requests from the European Commission with completion expected by the end of 2025, regarding e.g. data carriers, unique identifiers, links between physical and digital representations, interoperability, access rights, and data processing and storage (CEN/CLC/JTC 24, 2024). Additionally, the details of DPP content will be defined for each product group through the CPR acquis process. This dual-approach ensures that the DPP is tailored to the diverse needs of stakeholders. As a result, stakeholders will be required to align their IT-systems and data formats with these emerging standards to ensure compliance, such as preparing their data and adapting their workflows.

3. Methods

To answer the research questions formulated in this study, semi-structured interviews and a survey were employed for the data collection process. In this section, the methods used for data collection and data analysis are described. The overall research process can be seen in Fig. 1.

3.1. Stakeholder semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews aimed to identify the benefits and barriers of the DPP, and to obtain insights from key stakeholders within the construction industry. This explanatory and exploratory interview type was selected for its versatility, flexibility and possibility for follow-up questions, while allowing comparable data (Saunders et al., 2007). Frequently used in qualitative research (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006), semi-structured interviews were deemed suitable for gaining insights into an emerging topic. Drawing on topics identified in the literature, an interview guide with five key themes was formulated: 1) circular economy, 2) data and traceability for circularity, 3) benefits of the DPP, 4) data requirements of the DPP, and 5) barriers and challenges

Fig. 1. The overall research process.

in implementing the DPP. During the research process, the interview guide was adjusted to remove questions deemed unnecessary, such as those related to circular economy, to improve relevance and streamline data collection. The interview guide is provided in the supplementary information.

The interview participants were carefully selected, as data quality directly affects the integrity of the study (Saunders et al., 2007). A purposeful sampling strategy was utilized, emphasizing the variation of participants, as according to the principles outlined by Palinkas et al. (2015). This approach is common in qualitative research to select information-rich participants related to the studied phenomenon (Palinkas et al., 2015). To guide this process, five stakeholder groups were first defined based on the end-users identified in the literature (see Section 2.1), adapted to the construction industry context, along with the DPP data requirements (see Section 2.1.2.) and building life-cycle stages (Adams et al., 2017). The groups include: 1) design and manufacturing, 2) construction, 3) end-of-life management, 4) research and development (R&D), and strategy, 5) government and policy bodies. To ensure a versatile research sample, interviewees were then selected to represent these stakeholder groups to ensure coverage across the value chain.

In total, 21 interviews were conducted. Among these, 18 were one-on-one interviews, while the remainder involved two participants (42,9 % represented design and manufacturing, 4,8 % construction, 4,8 % end-of-life management, 23,8 % R&D and strategy, 23,8 % government and policy bodies). The majority represented an organization in Finland ($n = 9$), whereas others from Belgium ($n = 4$), Germany ($n = 3$), France ($n = 1$), Italy ($n = 1$), Netherlands ($n = 1$), Norway ($n = 1$) and Spain ($n = 1$). Further details can be found in the supplementary information.

3.2. Survey

The aim of the survey was to collect standardised quantitative data to supplement and validate findings of the interviews. This deductive approach enables efficient data collection from a larger sample prior to quantitative analysis, and allows for easy comparison of responses (Saunders et al., 2007). The outline was developed in alignment with the research questions, background study, and interview guide, focusing on three central areas: 1) benefits of the DPP, 2) data content requirements of the DPP, and 3) barriers in implementing the DPP. The survey consisted of 28 close-ended questions, with additional optional open-ended questions allowing respondents to elaborate on their answers. The survey questionnaire is found in the supplementary information. The

survey was distributed to experts in the construction industry within the extended network of colleagues involved in the ICEBERG- and CISUFLO-EU projects.

A total of 47 responses were gathered. Due to anonymity of the survey, there is a possibility of overlap between interviewees and survey respondents. The survey respondents, similarly to the interviewees, were categorized into key stakeholder groups (51 % R&D and strategy, 26 % design and manufacturing, 9 % government and policy bodies, 8 % construction, 6 % end-of-life management). The majority represented large enterprises (32 respondents), while others medium-sized enterprises (6), small enterprises (6) and micro-sized enterprises (3). Organizations were represented from several European countries (19 % Belgium, 19 % Finland, 15 % Spain, 11 % Italy, 11 % the Netherlands, 9 % the United Kingdom, 4 % Denmark, 4 % Turkey, 2 % France, 2 % Germany, 2 % Greece, 2 % Luxembourg). Further details can be found in the supplementary information.

3.3. Data analysis

Thematic analysis was used to systematically identify, analyse and report patterns of qualitative data. This method is recognized as a foundational approach in qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), due to its flexibility and applicability to several types of data types, samples and methodological approaches. Given the exploratory nature of this study and the objectives, thematic analysis was deemed as a suitable method for analysing the collected interview data. Thematic analysis includes steps of data familiarization, generation of initial codes, theme search, theme review, defining and naming themes, and report production (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The interview data was coded using a qualitative data analysis software, NVivo, which enhanced data organization and rigor. Four key themes were identified: the benefits of the DPP, implementation barriers, data content needs and conditions for efficient implementation.

4. Results

This section presents and interprets the findings from the interviews and survey, with each subsection surrounding around each research question of the study.

4.1. Benefits of the digital product passport

Key topics on the benefits of the DPP highlighted in the stakeholder engagement include traceability, BIM-integration, and resource

efficiency. In the survey, respondents ranked statements on benefits, with traceability emerging as the most prevalent, followed by facilitation of certification processes and hindering of greenwashing. Fig. 2 presents these results in a color-coded heatmap, displaying the preferences of stakeholder groups.

Interviewees strongly agreed that the DPP improves traceability and saves resources, in terms of time, costs, and workload, with time savings being the most frequently mentioned. The primary benefits arise directly from the information it provides, with direct access to this data being highly valued. Product information management emerged as a key topic, with participants acknowledging the need for improved data management. However, traceability systems remain underutilized, lacking a unified system connecting all actors. Through improved information management and systematic data collection, the DPP was stated to

eliminate issues of scattered data and avoid unnecessary replication. Systematic data sharing and clear content presentation was stated to further enhance accessibility. Further workload reductions were stated to stem from a centralized information source, streamlining decision-making. This would enable end-users to efficiently compare environmental impacts, costs, evaluate durability and find appropriate replacement products. The DPP was believed to improve the competitive advantage for organizations, by enhancing perceived reliability or by being considered an asset. Moreover, it streamlines project planning and execution, by organizing logistics and transportation during the construction phase, and by efficient resource allocation.

The benefits of traceability were seen as multifaceted: enabling designers to access information quickly, contractors to manage timelines, and government agencies to improve policy processes. It was also seen

Fig. 2. Survey results of statements ranked on a Likert scale. Darker green shades represent higher level of agreement, while lighter green to white shades indicate lower level of agreement relative to other statements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

as a means to improve demolition, dismantling and recycling practices. The DPP especially fosters circular practices such as extending product lifespans, including selecting products for specific purposes and managing building life cycles. A digital representation of material proportions within a structure, including recycled content, was seen as further facilitating product assessment. Tracing product history facilitates reuse by addressing quality uncertainties, which currently makes customers reluctant to invest in reused products, which is a challenge particularly in the construction industry, where products often have lower integral value compared to virgin resources.

Integrating DPP with BIM was mainly seen as an accelerator for further digitalizing the sector. This integration would then be especially effective in demolition processes, as it would aid in recycling different products and provides a comprehensive overview of the building. Modelling materials used in structures and their impact on air quality was also identified as in need of development. As data accumulates, improved modelling solutions could be widely disseminated, helping to identify solutions that produce better indoor air quality. BIM was also seen as having potential in addressing a foreseen problem related to the placement density of physical tags, also making it a more cost-effective solution. Vinyl flooring was highlighted as a good example of being relatively inexpensive, where reducing the tag density through BIM could keep the costs minimal in proportion to the product.

Steel structures were suggested for prioritization in the phased implementation of the DPP for their ease of handling and reuse, along with the major environmental benefits. Concrete products were also seen as a good option, although their complexity could make information management challenging due to onsite modifications. Also flooring products were discussed and specifically the use of additives that are likely to become hazardous in the future. Survey results show that concrete, plastic and insulation products would benefit most from a DPP with regard to circularity. It was also proposed that the phased implementation should align with the ongoing revision of standardization mandates in the CPR.

4.2. Data content needs of the digital product passport

Stakeholder engagement through interviews and survey demonstrates a broad consensus on the data content needs of the DPP. These include manufacturing, usage, end-of-life and life-cycle, with a particular emphasis on material composition information – especially hazardous substances – and end-of-life data.

Interviewees consistently deemed all data types as relevant to include in the DPP, with manufacturing data emerging as the most critical, more specifically, the technical data, product composition, quality of raw materials (e.g. possible contaminations), physical and chemical properties, recycled content and other product information. Environmental data, such as the carbon footprints and EPDs, were also frequently highlighted. Additionally, technical instructions for product use and maintenance, and user manuals were also considered important.

Interviewees also highlighted the need for comprehensive hazardous substance information, including substance type, characteristics, and behaviour under different conditions (e.g. heating). Any hazardous substances potentially released during recycling should be clearly reported to ensure safety. Information on REACH compliance should be included to address all regulatory requirements. One interviewee highlighted the importance of specifying both the amount and type of plasticizers in flooring materials, as recycled materials could contain several plasticizers, making it crucial to know exactly what materials are recycled.

Recyclability emerged as a key theme in interviews, with interviewees requesting detailed information on the potential for recycling or reuse, along with specific guidelines on the required technologies and processes. To facilitate recycling logistics, the DPP could provide information on suitable recycling locations or facilities. While the role of the DPP in enhancing recycling practices enhanced was highlighted, its

importance varied by product group. For example, one interviewee in the flooring industry stated that recycling instructions are less critical, as they can recycle all incoming products. Another interviewee in the same industry stated that all post-consumer materials should be assumed to contain legacy additives. One interviewee noted that recyclers frequently ask the same questions regarding materials and product composition.

Interviewees highlighted the need for ensuring correct, up-to-date and validated information. While some noted that a DPP should include an appropriate level of detail – avoiding excessive data for the sake of data itself – others underscored that data currently perceived irrelevant may become valuable in the future. As such, they cautioned against prematurely excluding any data, as it is unclear which data might support future use cases. The need for standardization was emphasized, particularly regarding data format, tools, software, methodology, and most critically, the content, calling for uniform and harmonized approaches. The interviewees emphasized the significance of engaging all actors to ensure the contribution of relevant data.

In the survey, stakeholders ranked various data examples based on relevance, as presented in Fig. 3 through a color-coded scheme indicating relative importance across stakeholder groups. Overall, end-of-life and life-cycle data received greatest emphasis. Among manufacturing data, information on material contents (including physical and chemical properties, potential hazardous materials and sources) was deemed the most important. Stakeholders in end-of-life management placed the greatest emphasis on manufacturing data, while R&D stakeholders considered it less important. Usage data was rated consistently across all stakeholder groups, but was regarded as the least important data category overall. End-of-life data was deemed most relevant, with recycling and disposal instructions including EPR obligations emerging as the most significant in comparison to other data examples across all data types. Finally, life-cycle data was also considered crucial, especially regarding environmental impacts and circularity performance.

Survey results further reveal that stakeholders in construction as well as design and manufacturing had similar relevance rankings. End-of-life management stakeholders consistently ranked all data types higher than other groups. Government and policy bodies prioritized end-of-life data, while stakeholders in R&D and strategy generally assigned lower scores.

4.3. Barriers and challenges in implementing the digital product passport

The most highlighted barrier in interviews was business confidentiality, which could become more challenging if the DPP requires more detailed information than current requirements, such as those in declarations of performance or environmental product declarations. Organizations might be unwilling to share data that includes details on product manufacturing, exact production settings, production emissions, certain additives, recipes and concentrations. This barrier was considered most significant for manufacturers, in the context of required data and the level of detail needed. Also, manufacturers may hesitate to share their data, as it could reveal e.g. production plant costs. Two interviewees noted that the DPP could reveal innovative product options or solutions. Data sharing incentives could include benchmarking, improved marketing strategies and validating environmental claims. Some interviewees believed that not all data has to be visible for everyone. Moreover, blockchain technology to address these issues was also suggested. Survey results show a strong consensus that business confidentiality presents a barrier.

In the interviews, time was not identified as a major barrier. Adapting to a new digital technology may necessitate time investments, however, the potential benefits would ultimately outweigh these efforts. Time was linked to the lifespan of buildings, highlighting the challenge of information management and maintaining its accuracy, which would also contribute with expenses. One interviewee strongly emphasized the challenge of ensuring that physical tags on flooring products can endure

Fig. 3. Survey results of data relevance for stakeholders. Darker green shades represent higher relevance, while lighter green to white shades indicate lower relevance relative to other data. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the entire lifespan, from installation to demolition. One interviewee underscored that as time is critical during demolition, the management of the DPP should not add delays. One interviewee suggested that time could hinder SMEs involved in low-profit-margin product categories, in contrast to larger organizations involved with high-turnover products. Survey results show broad agreement that limited resources for data input and processing present a challenge.

Most survey respondents considered limited IT-knowledge as a barrier, while some interviewees cited IT-architecture, its management and system continuity as challenges instead. Should the DPP require implementation of a new software, time could present a more significant obstacle. One interviewee considered the IT-expertise a more significant barrier than business confidentiality, especially in the construction sector with its low digitalization and complex value chains. Larger suppliers, contractors, and clients often have access to various programs and tools, gaining an advantage over those in lower levels of the value chain. Especially SMEs may need to outsource IT-tasks, leading to additional financial burdens. Survey responses show a strong consensus on financing aspects as a barrier, however, there was no clear correlation with the organization size.

The policy landscape was discussed in interviews. The legislation should avoid excessively interfering with the DPP content, allowing it to remain market-oriented. It should be flexible enough to accommodate for changes over time. The regulation should specifically align with the

EU-internal market system, regarding manufacturer information, product characteristics, third-party verification and other essential data and submission formats. Moreover, the timeline for of the different stages in the development of the DPP and related standardizations should be clearer for actors.

4.4. Analysis of conditions related to efficient implementation of the digital product passport in the construction sector

The benefits and data content requirements of the DPP were discussed in relation to effective implementation during the interviews.

Firstly, conditions regarding accessibility, such as the availability and feasibility of the DPP, were frequently mentioned. To ensure effective implementation, all actors must be involved in the planning process of the DPP, with an emphasis on SMEs to prevent financial strain, while also reducing the necessity for policy interventions. To foster growth for both SMEs and larger organizations, market interventions should be proportionate to the organization size. Moreover, contribution of relevant data and engaging all actors is necessary to ensure full traceability and transparency.

Secondly, conditions concerning data quality and information management were addressed, with stakeholders emphasizing the importance of accurate, up-to-date, validated and reliable information. Several interviewees noted that the DPP should contain an appropriate level of

detail of information and avoid excessive data without purpose, which improves the DPP's effectiveness in resource saving.

Thirdly, conditions related to standardization require uniformity in areas such as data format, methodology, tools and software. A harmonized approach is needed, while ensuring capacities for system flexibility, allowing for continuous development.

The stakeholders can be divided into practicing stakeholders, which form the value chains in the construction sector; governance, which is the supervisory authority; and R&D, which can be seen as a spectator without a specific impact on the sector. Specifically in the topic of data it became evident that R&D has very different interests in the DPP – focusing on technical data, whereas the practicing stakeholders and supervising authority showed more interest in the data that is relevant for practicalities, such as end-of-life management of products.

Moreover, stakeholder perceptions remain uncertain, particularly in the construction industry, which encompasses vast, complex global value chains with diverse products and subsectors. These uncertainties are further compounded with uncertainties in the timeline regarding regulations, standardization and implementation, as well as questions about how the DPP will function in practice. Stakeholder engagement revealed limited familiarity with the topic, with many participants indicating that their organizations neither currently use a DPP nor plan to.

5. Discussion

The construction sector is currently characterized by a linear economy, although it has strong potential to transition to a circular economy (Hossain et al., 2020). To support this transition, the European Commission (2024a) has proposed a mandatory DPP to support sharing product data with the entire value chain. However, since the DPP lacks specifications for the construction industry, stakeholders remain uncertain about its implementation and potential impact. To address the lack of awareness, this study set out to map stakeholder perceptions, including their views on potential benefits, necessary data content, and implementation challenges. This study contributes to an emerging body of research in the construction industry within the European context, and helps address a key data gap highlighted by Jensen et al. (2023).

The current information and communication gaps in the sector underscore the necessity for a traceability system, with findings suggesting that the DPP can fill these gaps. Table 2 presents the identified data and knowledge gaps along with the information provided by the DPP to fill these gaps as well as links to relevant regulations.

The study demonstrates that enhanced resource efficiency as well as facilitated decision-making can be achieved with providing manufacturing, usage, life-cycle and end-of-life data, aligning with the findings of Plociennik et al. (2022b). The results are widely in agreement with existing literature (e.g. Adisorn et al., 2021; Plociennik et al., 2022a), though most address a non-specific industry with only a few focusing specifically on the construction sector (e.g. Götz et al., 2022; Heinrich & Lang, 2019).

Findings show that data management improves significantly with the DPP, supporting the view that long-term systematic data utilization could introduce novel data processing methods, particularly when integrated with tools such as AI. Combining BIM with DPP would further advance digitalization in the sector. These integrations could further aid development of, for instance, predictive statistical models based on the performance data, such as sustained damages and their effects on the lifespan. Over time, accumulated data provides more insights into processes and progress tracking, particularly in procurement and inventory management. By enabling more efficient project coordination, facilitating reusability assessments, and ensuring the proper implementation of end-of-life practices, the DPP has the potential to improve construction and demolition waste management, a major challenge in the sector. Thus, the DPP is expected to significantly contribute to waste prevention and reduction. Despite the expected benefits of the DPP, this study does

Table 2

Identified data and knowledge gaps, the information in the DPP to fill these gaps as well as examples of relevant regulations and policies.

Data needs and knowledge gaps	Information provided in the DPP for overcoming barriers and ensuring effective implementation of environmental goals	Relevant regulations and policies (examples, not exhaustive)
Material content data	Content information for selection of toxic free materials	EU toxic free environment (European Commission, 2020b); POP regulation setting restrictions for the content of POP substances in feeds/ secondary raw materials (European Commission, 2019); REACH regulation No 1907/2006 on substances on the Authorisation List (REACH Art. 57, Annex XIV) (European Commission, 2006) and Candidate List of substances of high concern (SVHC list, in accordance with REACH Article 59(10)), ECHAs SCIP database setting reporting obligations (ECHA, 2025); Substitution of hazardous substances using the Safe and sustainable by design framework (European Commission, 2022b)
	Emission data of products for selection of low-emitting products. Conformity with product limits and emissions as per national legislation for use (e.g. indoor air emission classes for chemical substances)	EU List for lowest concentration of interest of chemical substances in indoor air environments (European Commission, 2023)
Environmental data	Information about the environmental impacts of a product throughout its lifecycle	Construction Products Regulation (CPR) sets mandatory requirements for reporting e.g. the global warming potential for construction products (European Commission, 2024a)
	Information for product comparison	Environmental product declarations (EPD) provide information for calculation of carbon dioxide emissions from buildings (national goals in several EU countries for new buildings)
	Recommendations for safe waste management	Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC (European Commission, 2018) (e.g. hazardous waste classification for end-of-life management, sorting of waste), EU construction & demolition waste management protocol including guidelines for pre-demolition and pre-renovation audits of construction works (

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Data needs and knowledge gaps	Information provided in the DPP for overcoming barriers and ensuring effective implementation of environmental goals	Relevant regulations and policies (examples, not exhaustive)
Circularity supporting information, resource efficiency, sustainability	Indicators for circularity (e. g. recycled content, durability) and sustainability (carbon footprint) to enhance awareness on environmentally sustainable products Information on impurities, separability of unwanted layers for enabling reuse and recycling Safe use and storage conditions for extending product lifetime and avoiding damage	European Commission, 2024c) Green Public Procurement as an instrument to drive market demand for sustainable and circular products (European Commission, 2008) Extended producer responsibility (EPR) for design of products with recycled content Initiatives related to digitalization in the construction sector for ensuring direct access to information for all actors throughout the value chain: Building information modelling (BIM) (for information on quantities, positions of construction product for recycling, reuse); Digital logbook for buildings, a comprehensive repository for building data (e.g. information about construction, maintenance, energy use, renovations, and performance monitoring). It may contain multiple DPPs for all the products that are part of a building

not quantify the specific impacts such as material recovery rates or resource savings, highlighting a gap further research could address.

As highlighted in the literature (e.g. Ducuing & Reich, 2023; Koppelaar et al., 2023; Walden et al., 2021), the main barrier pertains to balancing business confidentiality and safeguarding intellectual property with ensuring transparency and traceability. Herein, manufacturers are the primary focus, as they provide most of the relevant data, highlighting their importance as information providers and stakeholders, as also discussed by Adisorn et al. (2021). To reduce their burden, Adisorn et al. (2021) proposes developing an approach that consolidates their information, with the system distributing it to stakeholders according to specific access rights. However, this might contradict the concept of full transparency, affecting the reliability.

Another key challenge involves ensuring effective adaptation of the DPP across different stakeholder groups and organization sizes while minimizing additional burdens. Particularly SMEs may face barriers regarding limited human resources, financial burdens and IT-expertise, placing them at a disadvantageous position. The findings further emphasize the need for including organizations of all sizes during the design stage of the DPP to prevent financial strains and imbalances. Nevertheless, given the scattered survey results on whether financing is a specific barrier for SMEs, conclusions should be made cautiously. Bernier et al. (2024) proposes recommendations to mitigate the challenges for SMEs through targeted support mechanisms, such as hands-on

training, collaborative initiatives with suppliers, stimulate adoption of standards by software vendors, or funding support programs to offset implementation costs.

The construction sector's wide variety of products makes it challenging to determine a single tool or framework to support traceability and the shift to a circular economy. To facilitate successful and widespread adoption of the DPP, findings indicate that phased implementation should prioritize short-lived products that quickly demonstrate the practical benefits. Conversely, Adisorn et al. (2021) emphasizes prioritizing product groups that can be implemented as quick as possible. Reflecting on this, our findings propose a complementary approach that considers criteria such as short lifespan, high standardization, and well-defined end-of-life processes as a suitable starting point.

Despite the qualitative nature of the study, we believe that it is well justified to support the findings, which highlight better resource efficiency linked to facilitated decision-making. Through accessing reliable, comparable data, actors are able to make informed choices and adopt circular practices, such as design for disassembly and adaptability. For instance, designers can utilize insights from previous DPPs on the product end-of-life, while downstream users in the value chain benefit from disassembly and reuse instructions. Insights into product management and wear throughout its life cycle enhance manufacturers' capabilities in resource utilization and product development. However, the results show that usage data was given the least emphasis regarding relevance, suggesting that as such information is not currently required by regulations, it is considered less critical to include and thus perceived as a burden for data input. This further indicates that the willingness to share data is limited to regulatory requirements. Findings emphasize the opinions that legislation should not overly interfere with the content, leaving the data content to be market-oriented. Regulation is considered rather slow, acting as obstacles rather than facilitators for the spread of optimal market practices.

The study identifies that the four data types function as a general guideline, with the suggested next steps focusing on defining specific product group data requirements, with manufacturers in central focus. For instance, steel products might necessitate detailed data on alloy composition and recycled content, while concrete products may require more data for assessing environmental impacts due to its complexity. Flooring products again emphasize more granular data on components like plasticizers, and insulation materials might necessitate more precise data on thermal performance and fire resistance. Moreover, the expected lifespan and product value may influence the level of detail and specific content, with products that have longer lifespans and higher value necessitating more detailed data. Future studies should therefore conduct more detailed stakeholder group specific data needs exploration, to specify the minimum and recommended content requirements tailored to the characteristics of different products. Another consideration is incorporating additional key stakeholder groups for different product groups, considering variations across value chains and organization sizes.

This study is subject to limitations, including a restricted number and depth of interviews, uneven stakeholder representation, and a geographic focus on Finland. Moreover, due to the anonymity of the survey, there is a possibility of overlap between interview and survey respondents. Translation nuances may have affected interpretation, and the wording of questions may have led to different interpretations, especially among non-native English speakers. Stakeholder engagement in interviews focused on general data requirements, concentrating on the four data types, instead of delving into specific elements. Other limitations involve response, confirmation and observer bias. The interviewee's familiarity with DPPs varied, possibly affecting the credibility. Importantly, as the concept and research surrounding the DPP is rapidly evolving, this dynamic context adds an additional layer of complexity and limitation to the study.

6. Conclusions

The DPP is a promising policy tool that facilitates the shift to a circular economy by offering practical and viable solutions for end-users. This study shows that improved resource efficiency, a centralized source of information, and facilitated decision-making are attributed as key benefits of the DPP, given their direct impact on the outcomes. Achieving these benefits requires data across the manufacturing, usage, end-of-life and life-cycle stages.

While these data types provide a general framework, the specific content should be customized for each product group, necessitating additional research to determine the precise data content needs of different stakeholder groups across construction product supply chains. Moving forward, establishing an optimal level of detail is necessary to balance transparency, data quality preservation, and compliance with intellectual property rights. This challenge is particularly significant given the long lifespan of construction products.

Another dimension to consider is the engagement of manufacturers in data sharing, given their central role concerning safeguarding business confidentiality. Striking a balance between transparency and business confidentiality is crucial. While full data transparency is ideal, it may not always be feasible. A key theme of the DPP is trust, but withholding data could undermine it, influencing stakeholder perceptions of the system. While this study focuses primarily on the practical and implementation-related aspects of the DPP, future research should explore how social aspects, such as organizational culture, stakeholder trust and training needs, affect its adoption, usability and effectiveness. Clear frameworks, well-defined access rights and active stakeholder engagement during the design phase are needed to build a robust and functional system.

This study contributes to ongoing efforts to align construction practices with circular economy principles, in light of evolving European regulatory frameworks and sustainable goals. While focused on the construction sector, the findings provide insights relevant to other sectors implementing DPPs, as they highlight the potential to drive sustainable practices. By promoting sustainable practices – such as improving resource efficiency, enabling better decision-making through data transparency, and fostering circularity – this work aligns with the key aspects of Sustainable Development Goal 12. Specifically, the DPP supports SDG 12 by encouraging more efficient use of materials, reducing waste across product life cycles, and facilitating the shift to a more sustainable supply chain management. Ultimately, the effectiveness of the DPP will depend on stakeholder usability, perceptions and acceptance. If these issues are not adequately addressed, the practicality and viability of the DPP may be compromised.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Winnie Ruismäki: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Malin zu Castell-Rüdenhausen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision. **Elina Pohjalainen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Margareta Wahlström:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2025.100275>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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